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Examining University Students' Knowledge, Attitudes, Beliefs, and Patterns of Water-Pipe Tobacco Smoking

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Abstract

Background: Water-pipe smoking is currently considered a global phenomenon among the adult population. However, no recent studies measured the knowledge, attitudes, beliefs, and patterns of use of water-pipe smoking among university students.

Purpose: The purpose of this research was to examine the knowledge, attitudes, and beliefs toward water-pipe tobacco smoking and patterns of use of water-pipe tobacco smoking among University students.

Methods: The study utilised a correlational design to examine the knowledge, attitudes, and beliefs toward water-pipe tobacco smoking and patterns of use of water-pipe tobacco smoking among university students. Around 435 students were selected using a convenience sampling technique. A self-administered questionnaire is utilised to collect the sample. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) was deployed to perform the analysis. Ethical approval was taken before collecting the data.

Results: The results showed that around 186 (42.7 %) of students tried a water pipe for smoking with their friends for the first time. 216 (49.6 %) used it at café for the first time, and 245 (56.3 %) used it in café most of the time. Around 430 (98.8 %) of students had a water pipe at home. The main reasons and drivers were stress, such as exams (mean=4.42), and enjoyment (mean=4.25). The central beliefs and attitudes toward water pipe smoking were the feeling of being addicted to water pipe smoking (mean=4.42) and the perceived that young people harm themselves by water pipe smoking (mean=4.39). The students perceived that water-pipe smoking could harm fetuses during pregnancy (mean=4.8), various types of cancer (lung, mouth, throat, etc. (mean=4.45), and heart disease (mean=4.41). There is a significant positive relationship between attitudes and beliefs toward water-pipe use with the level of knowledge and a negative relationship to quitting water-pipe smoking and related factors. Moreover, there is a positive relationship between knowledge level with intention to quit water-pipe smoking and related factors.

Conclusion: The pattern of water pipe use did not significantly differ from other countries in the Middle East. Moreover, despite the positive overall perception of university students toward water pipes, many perceived items showed the need for more efforts regarding this problem in both genders to encourage students to stop the use of water pipes by controlling the drivers, enhancing positive knowledge and beliefs.

Keywords: Attitudes, Beliefs, Patterns of Use, Smoking, Water-pipe, University of Jordan, University Students

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Introduction

Water-pipe smoking is a way of tobacco consumption smoking flavoured or non-flavoured tobacco using a single or multi-stemmed device to pass the smoke through water or other fluid (WHO, 2015). Water-pipe smoking is currently considered a global phenomenon among the adult population. It is induced by several drivers, including the emergence of flavoured tobacco (Maassel), the interaction between the rising café culture

and the water's social dimension, the development of media, the absence of regulatory/policy related to the water-pipe (Maziak et al., 2015).

According to a new survey of 152 colleges and universities in the US, 8.4% of students currently use the water pipe for smoking (Primack et al., 2013). Two recent studies showed that the prevalence of water-pipe tobacco smoking use was higher than cigarette smoking

in Western societies. The first study, which was carried out among 2399 students, indicated that the prevalence of water-pipe tobacco smoking prevalence was 7.6%, while cigarette smoking was 3.4% (Jawad et al., 2013). The second, carried out among 1203 participants indicated that the prevalence of water pipe used for the past year was 28.4% while cigarette smoking was 19.6%. There is around a 6.3% increase in ever water-pipe

Many studies and reports showed severe many health effects of water-pipe tobacco smoking use. The laboratory analyses showed that water-pipe smoke has significant carcinogens and toxicants. Carcinogens include volatile aldehydes like formaldehyde, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, tobacco-specific nitrosamines, and benzene. Toxicants include heavy metals and nitric oxide. The burning of charcoal produces carbon monoxide (CO) at a high level (WHO, 2015; Fong et al., 2018;). Studies showed that water-pipe smoke elevates blood pressure and heart rate (Al-Kubati et al., 2006; Alomari et al., 2014), increases lung inflammation and impaired lung function (Hawari et al., 2013), and increases the risk of acute CO poisoning (La Fauci et al., 2012) which can lead to multiple chronic diseases such as periodontal disease, cancer (oral, lung, gastric, esophageal, and urinary bladder) (Jacob et al., 2013; Mamtani et al., 2017; Waziry, et al., 2017), chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (Hawari et al., 2013), cardiovascular disease, stroke, chronic rhinitis, low birth weight, (Alomari et al., 2014; El-Zaatari et al., 2015), and impaired mental health (Bandiera et al., 2016).

Although water-pipe smoking has emerged for many centuries, the majority of users are yet unaware of its severe impacts on health (Yadav & Rawal, 2018). Worldwide, few studies discussed water-pipe tobacco smoking in terms of users' knowledge beliefs, attitudes, and patterns of use and their relationships, especially among university students who are considered an important age group due to its role in the future and development of their countries (WHO, 2005; Maziak et al., 2015).

The purpose of this research was to identify the knowledge, attitudes, and beliefs toward water-pipe tobacco smoking and patterns of using water-pipe smoking, and to identify the relationship between knowledge, attitudes, and beliefs toward water-pipe tobacco smoking among the University students.

Knowing the knowledge, attitudes, beliefs, drivers, and patterns of water-pipe tobacco smoking use is considered key for authorities and health managers to develop proper prevention policies and strategies to compact this type of smoking which subsequently leads to improved national economic and social status and decline the burden on health systems.

Research Method

(Barnett et al., 2013). Many standardised surveillance systems showed a significant growth in water-pipe tobacco smoking. For example, the data of two years (2011–2012) from the National Youth Tobacco Survey in the US showed around a 32% increase in current water-pipe smoking (CDC, 2013). The Canadian Youth Smoking Survey showed smokers (Czoli et al., 2013),

Design and Setting

The study used descriptive correlational design to examine the knowledge, attitudes, and beliefs toward water-pipe smoking and patterns of water-pipe smoking use among University students. The correlational design is utilized to present the general overview of the specific phenomenon and examine the relationships between the variables (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). The study was conducted at the University of Jordan (UJ), Amman, Jordan.

Sample

The adequate sample size for this study was 381 which was determined based on a 5% margin of error and a 95% confidence interval (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). However, around 460 students were recruited to decrease the risk of withdrawal from study and possible refusal. It was calculated by adding around 20% of the minimal sample to the calculated sample. A convenience sampling technique was used to select the participants from different schools. There were many inclusion criteria considered in the selection of the sample including the students should have Jordanian nationality to ensure adequate generalization of results to all study populations, a study in UJ, use or previously used water for smoking, accepting the participation in the study and sign the consent forms before data collection.

Instrument

A self-administered questionnaire was used to collect the data. The questionnaire had six sections. The first section was the demographic data section (8 items) aimed to collect general demographic information about students.

The second section was the patterns of water-pipe use section (18 items) aimed to describe the use of water-pipe smoking including water-pipe smoking status, prevalence rate, length of use at this rate, age of starting water-pipe smoking, and availability of water-pipe at home. Most of these items were retrieved from many studies in the literature (Dar-Odeh et al., 2010; Smith-Simone et al., 2008).

The third section was the drivers and reasons for water-pipe smoking section (14 items) aimed to explore the main drivers leading to the use water-pipe for smoking including the perception regarding the water-pipe smoking roles in communication with others, getting rid of stressors, relaxation, overcoming the boring, leisure,

water-pipe smoking under stress and holidays. Most of these items were retrieved from many studies in the literature (Akl et al., 2013; Kelishadi et al., 2007).

The fourth section was the attitudes and beliefs toward water-pipe use section (15 items) aimed to explore the perceptions of students to water-pipe use including badness of water-pipe use, acceptance from family and community, its roles in making the person fun and energetic, its effects on health, and the difficulty of quitting the water-pipe. Most of these items were retrieved from many studies in the literature (Eshah & Froelicher, 2018; Noonan, 2013). Likert scale (1-5)

The fifth section was the level of knowledge about the health effects of water-pipe smoking (15 items) including the knowledge regarding the harmful chemicals, nicotine, carcinogenic substances, and heavy metals in smoke from water-pipe, and the possibility of causing heart diseases, cancer infertility, and harm fetuses during pregnancy. Most of these items were retrieved from many studies in the literature (Jacob et al., 2013; Primack et al., 2008, 2013).

Likert scale (1-5) was used to score the students' answers in the third, fourth, and fifth sections where one indicated a strongly disagree while five indicated strongly agree. The total score for this section was calculated by the sum of all items' means.

The sixth section was the intension to quit the water-pipe smoking section (15 items) aimed to identify the students' intention to stop the water-pipe and related factors including the plan to stop water-pipe smoking, get ride addiction, get better shape, improve the quality of life, and perform the exercise; problems at works or with family, pregnant or had children Most of these items were retrieved from many studies in the literature (Smith-Simone et al., 2008). Yes, and No answers were adopted for each statement, however, to make a correlation where the No scored one while yes scored 2. The reliability and validity of the questionnaire were measured by researchers. Construct validity was measured and showed that the eigenvalue proportion was more than 1, and the factor loadings for sections were more than 0.4. Cronbach's alpha was measured and showed that the coefficient was 0.72 for all questionnaires and more than 0.60 for each section.

Data Analysis

The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) was deployed for the data analysis, including descriptive and inferential analyses. The descriptive statistics were aimed at exploring the demographic data of students and identifying their perception of study variables. Inferential statistics were used to evaluate the construct validity questionnaire by utilizing Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) and reliability by utilizing Cronbach's alpha. The chi-square test and T-test were used to measure the difference between variables results of data according to gender, where the t-test was used for

continuous data while the Chi-square test was used for categorical data. Pearson's correlation coefficient was used to identify the relationship between variables.

Ethical Consideration

Ethical permission was taken from UJ before conducting the study to protect and ensure the rights of the participants, data confidentiality, the right to full disclosure or withdrawal, and the self-determination of students.

Results

Sample Characteristics

The response rate was 94.5%. Of 435 students, 301 (69%) students were male. The mean of students' age was 20.01. All participating students were single. Most of the students, 46.2%, had less than 500 JD of family income. 45.9% of students from medical schools. 120 (27.5%) studied in the second academic year. 390 (89.6%) live at the family house during their studies. The mean GPA was 3.11/4. See Table 1.

Table 1: Characteristics of Respondents

Characteristics	Total N=435
Age Per Year (Mean, SD)	20.1 (2.11)
Marital Status (N, %)	
• Single	435 (100%)
• Married	0 (0%)
Family Income Per JD (N, %)	
• Less than 500 JD	201 (46.2%)
• 500-1000 JD	182 (41.8%)
• More than 1000 JD	52 (12.0%)
School	
• Social	190 (43.6%)
• Medical	200 (45.9%)
• Science	45 (10.5%)
Academic Years	
• 1 st year	90 (20.7%)
• 2 nd year	120 (27.5%)
• 3 rd year	105 (24.1%)
• 4 th year	120 (28.6%)
GPA (Mean, SD)	3.11 (1.01)
Place of Residence	
• Family House	390 (89.6%)
• Students' house (Alone)	10 (2.2%)
• Students' house (With others)	35 (8.0%)

Pattern of Water-pipe Use

The results showed the average cost of water pipe use per month among students was 45 JD. 191 (43.9%) smoked a cigarette while 200 (46.2%) are currently using water pipes. The average age to start the use of the water pipe was 15 years old. 122 (28.0%) used a water pipe every week. 210 (48.3%) used it at this rate

for 1-3 years. 186 (42.7 %) used a water pipe with their friends for the first time, while 285 (65.5 %) used it currently with their friends. 216 (49.6 %) used it at café for the first time, and 245 (56.3 %) used it in café most of the time. 430 (98.8 %) had a water pipe at home.

After using the water pipe smoking, 20 students (4.5%) felt nauseous and vomited. 429 students (98.7 %) preferred a water-pipe with flavor. 135 students (31.0%) intend to stop water-pipe use. However, 200 students (45.9%) tried to stop it more than one time. The average time since the last serious attempt to stop water pipe smoking per month was 16. See Table 2.

Table 2: Pattern of Water-pipe Use

Pattern	Total n=435
Cost of Water use per month (Mean, SD)	45 (7.21)
Cigarette Smoking Status (n, %)	
• Current Smokers	191 (43.9%)
• Previous Smokers	152 (34.9%)
• Non Smokers	102 (23.4%)
Water-pipe Smoking Status (n, %)	
• Current Smokers	200 (46.2%)
• Smoked a few times but did not participate in full smoking sessions	184 (41.8%)
• Previous Smokers	52 (12.0%)
Rate of Water-pipe Smoking (n, %)	
• Daily	92 (21.1%)
• Weekly	122 (28.0%)
• 2-3 per week	102 (23.4%)
• Monthly	113 (25.9%)
How long have you smoked water at this rate? (n, %)	
• Less than 1 year	185 (42.5%)
• 1-3 years	210 (48.3%)
• More than 3 years	40 (9.2%)
At what age did you start water-pipe smoking? (Mean, SD)	15 (1.75)
The first use of the water pipe was accompanied by: (n, %)	
• Alone	180 (41.4%)
• with a friend or more	186 (42.7 %)
• with family	50 (11.5%)
• with a group of family and friends	19 (4.3%)
Generally, I smoked the water pipe (n, %)	
• Alone	130 (29.8%)
• with a friend or more	285 (65.5 %)
• with family	31 (7.1%)
• with a group of family and friends	9 (2.0%)
The place of the first use of the water pipe (n, %)	
• Home	200 (57.9%)
• Café	216 (49.6 %)
• Friend house	19 (4.3%)
In most cases, where do you smoke water? (n, %)	
• Home	180 (41.3%)

• Café	245 (56.3 %)
• Friend house	10 (2.2%)
Do you have a water pipe at home? (n, %)	
• Yes	430 (98.8 %)
• No	5 (1.2%)
The average duration of a water-pipe smoking session (n, %)	
• Less than 30 min	19 (4.3%)
• 30-60 min	180 (41.4%)
• 60-120 min	186 (42.7 %)
• More than 120 min	50 (11.5%)
After using the water pipe smoking, I feel	
• Nausea and Vomiting	20 (4.5%)
• Difficulty breathing	14 (3.2%)
• Chest pain the next day	14 (3.2%)
• All the above	0 (0%)
• Nothing	0 (0%)
	401 (92.2%)
Preferred Flavor (n, %)	
• With flavor	429 (98.7 %)
• Without flavor	6 (1.3%)
Do you intend to quit water-pipe smoking? (n, %)	
• Yes	135 (31.0%)
• No	300 (68.9%)
Have you ever tried to quit water-pipe smoking? (n, %)	
• No	190 (43.6%)
• One time	45 (10.5%)
• More than one time	200 (45.9%)
How long has it been since the last serious attempt to stop water-pipe smoking per month? (Mean, SD)	16 (3)

Study Variables: Drivers and Reasons,

As Table 3 shows. The main reasons and drivers according to students' perceptions were the increasing water-pipe use in times of stress such as exams (mean=4.42, SD=.38) and relaxation (mean=4.36, SD=.41), and smell enjoyment (mean=4.25, SD=.37). The main beliefs and attitudes toward water-pipe smoking according to students' perceptions were feeling of being fond of water-pipe smoking (mean=4.42, SD= 0.51), and perceived that young people harm themselves by water-pipe smoking (mean=4.39, SD= 0.47) and the community around the students accepts the water-pipe smoking (mean=4.34, SD=0.22).

The main perceived statements according to students' perceptions were that water-pipe smoking could harm fetuses during pregnancy (mean=4.8, SD=0.63), water-pipe Smoking may cause various types of cancer (lung, mouth, throat, etc. (mean=4.45, SD=0.59), and water-pipe smoking may cause heart disease (mean=4.41, SD=0.43). Finally, the results showed that the most perceived statements were that the students were able to finish the work, the students wanted to take care of the outer appearance, the students wanted to improve the

quality of life, and the students wanted to get a better shape.

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Table 3: Summary of Variables

Variables	Mean (SD)
Drivers and Reasons (Five Likert Scale)	
· I see it as a good way to communicate between friends and family	3.49 (.41)
· Helps get rid of stressors	4.14 (.21)
· Help me to relax	4.03 (.22)
· Something to do when I feel bored	2.87(.11)
· I use the water pipe smoking for leisure	3.72(.41)
· I enjoy its taste	4.01(.21)
· I enjoy its smell	4.25(.37)
· Help me to not smoke cigarettes	3.91(.29)
· Help me to control my appetite for food	3.78(.31)
· Help me to control my weight	3.74(.22)
· I smoke water pipes due to the influence of friends and family	2.82(.27)
· I use the water pipe smoking, so I do not feel like I'm different when I'm with a smoker	2.72(.17)
· My use of water pipe smoking is increasing in times of stress such as exams	4.42(.38)
· I use the water pipe smoking more often in times of relaxation such as holidays	4.36(.41)
Attitudes and Beliefs (Five Likert Scale)	
· I think water pipe smoking is usually not bad	1.04(0.11)
· My family accepts my smoking of the water pipe	3.07(0.31)
· The community around me accepts the water pipe smoking	4.34(0.22)
· The community around me accepts water pipe smoking more than cigarette smoking	4.22(0.58)
· I think the people who use water pipe smoke have more friends	3.81(0.41)
· I think that water pipe smoking makes the person appear more fun and energetic	3.88(0.21)
· I think young people harm themselves by water pipe smoking	4.39(0.47)
· I think that water pipe smoking for one or two years does not harm health	1.52(0.11)
· I think water pipe smoking is less harmful to health than cigarette smoking	1.78(0.17)
· I am not concerned about the health damage that may be caused to me by water pipe smoking	1.44(0.22)
· I believe that scientific evidence on the extent of the harm to health is very much exaggerated	3.63(0.38)
· I think that if I quit water pipe smoking early, the health damage caused by it can go away	3.72(0.17)
· I consider myself fond of water pipe smoking	4.42(0.51)
· I feel that water pipe smoking quitting smoking is difficult	2.36(0.37)
· I have been able to stop water pipe smoking at any time	2.53(0.29)
Level of knowledge (Five Likert Scale)	
· Inhaled smoke from water pipes contains harmful chemicals	4.2(0.58)
· Water pipe Smoking is addictive	3.18(0.39)
· Water pipe Smoking may cause various types of cancer (lung, mouth, throat, etc.)	4.45(0.59)
· Water pipe Smoking may cause heart disease	4.41(0.43)
· Water pipe Smoking can cause infertility in men who smoke	1.86(0.17)
	4.8(0.63)

· Water pipe Smoking can harm fetuses during pregnancy	4.39(0.51)
· Water pipe smoke contains more tar than cigarette smoke	2.68(0.38)
· Water pipe smoke contains more nicotine than cigarette smoke	3.96(0.32)
· Water pipe smoke contains more carcinogenic substances than cigarette smoke	3.11(0.22)
· Water pipe smoke contains more heavy metals than cigarette smoke	4.11(0.38)
· Water pipe Smoking is harmful to non-smokers who exposed to smoke	41.15(4.6)
Intention to Quit	
· I want to stop water pipe smoking	1.42(0.02)
· I have already stopped water pipe smoking a week ago	1.00(0.01)
· Currently, I have no problems at work	1.37(0.02)
· Currently, I do not have any family problems	1.41(0.02)
· I want to get rid of addiction	1.42(0.02)
· I exercise / I have the intention to exercise	1.21(0.02)
· I want to get a better shape	1.76(0.02)
· I want to take care of my outer appearance	1.97(0.03)
· I am pregnant / my wife is pregnant	1.00(0.01)
· I have small children	1.00(0.00)
· Currently, my mood is clear	1.51(0.02)
· Normally, I finish my work	1.99(0.03)
· Normally, I am calm and relaxed	1.51(0.02)
· Normally, my weight is fixed	1.75(0.03)
· I want to improve the quality of my life	1.80(0.02)

4.9 Relationships Between Study Variables

The results showed that there was a significant negative relationship between the reasons and drivers to use water and intention to quit the water-pipe smoking and related factors ($r=-.421$, p value= .004), a significant positive relationship between attitudes and beliefs toward water-pipe use and level of knowledge regarding the impact water-pipe smoking on health ($r=-.500$, p value= .000), negative relationship between it and intention to quit the water-pipe smoking and related factors ($r=-.381$, p value= .031), and a significant positive relationship between level of knowledge regarding the impact water-pipe smoking on health, and intention to quit the water-pipe smoking and related factors ($r=-.469$, p value= .000).

Discussion

This study is considered one of the first comprehensive studies regarding waterpipe smoking. Regarding the patterns of water-pipe use among university students, the results showed the average cost of water-pipe use per month among students was 45 JD. The cost is considered very high when knowing that the poverty line was JD.336 per capita per year. [1]. This indicated that smoking is considered a serious economic and health problem knowing that around 43.9% of university students are currently smoking a cigarette, and the average age of starting the use of the water pipe was 15 years old.

The results indicated the role of growing the café culture in starting water-pipe use, as showed in many studies that considered the rising café culture as the main driver to start water-pipe smoking and play an important role in starting water-pipe use among adolescents, as explained by many students. [2, 3]. The results indicated the role of the development of flavours that have different tastes, which are also considered a main driver to start water-pipe use in many studies where more than 98% in our sample preferred water with flavour. (Borgan et al., 2013; Maziak et al., 2015; Feirman et al., 2016).

Many studies in the literature showed that university students had many stressors related to exams and financial and social issues (Thawabieh & Qaisy, 2012; Regehr et al., 2013; Rosiek et al., 2016). This may explain the increasing water-pipe use in times of stress, smell enjoyment, getting rid of the stressors, and helping in relaxation. In Jordan, many studies indicated that the availability of many resources to develop stress with a lack of social support among university students (Hamdan-Mansour & Dawani, 2008; Hamdan-Mansour, 2010). However, inappropriate education and awareness regarding stress management can lead to the use of nonhealthy techniques for relaxation such as smoking (Al-Naggar et al., 2011; Abu-Helalah et al., 2015; Rosiek et al., 2016).

Moreover, students perceived that the community around them accepts water pipe smokers more than cigarette smokers. This may have been explained by the growing café culture and the extent of smoking

problems among all family members and friends, lack of education regarding smoking problems, the development of media, and the absence of regulations/policies related to the water pipe. These results are consistent with many previous studies (Dar-Odeh et al., 2013; Jawad et al., 2013; Malik et al., 2013; Sidani et al., 2018).

The results showed that the most perceived statements were that the students finish work, the students want to

take care of outer appearance, the students want to improve the quality of their life, and the students want to get a better shape. These results are expected especially among university students aged between 18-22 where the students want to improve the quality of their life, and the students want to get a better shape and take care of the outer appearance (Al-Ruzzieh & Ayaad 2022; Ayaad & Ayaad 2022; Ayaad et al., 2023)

Table 8: Relationship between study variables

		Mean (SD)	Drivers to Water-pipe Smoking	Attitudes and Beliefs Toward Water-pipe Use	Level of knowledge regarding the impact of water-pipe smoking on health	Intention to Quit the Water-pipe Smoking
Drivers to Water-pipe Smoking	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	52.26(3.99)	1			
Attitudes and Beliefs Toward Water-pipe Use	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	46.15(4.53)	.032 .09	1		
Level of knowledge regarding the impact of water-pipe smoking on health	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	41.15(4.60)	.044 .07	.500 .00*	1	
Intention to Quit the Water-pipe Smoking	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	22.12(0.26)	-.421 .004*	-.381 .031*	.469 .00*	1

*Significant at alpha=0.05 level

The results indicated that the increased perception of reasons and drivers to use water pipes leads to a decrease in the intention to quit water-pipe smoking and related factors. This result is expected, especially the drivers to water-pipe smoking is stronger, which makes stopping water-pipe use very hard. The results indicated that the increased perception of attitudes and beliefs toward water-pipe use leads to an increase in the perception of the level of knowledge regarding the impact of water-pipe smoking on health and a decrease in the perception of intention to quit water-pipe smoking and related factors. (Mamtani et al., 2017; Tucktuck et al., 2017; Waziry, et al., 2017).

Many items in the knowledge section are close to the attitudes section, such as the impact of water on health-related items. Moreover, the attitudes and beliefs result from the level of knowledge. So, the relationship between attitudes and beliefs toward water-pipe use and level of

knowledge is expected. This may also be used to explain the positive relationship between the level of knowledge regarding the impact of water-pipe smoking on health and the intention to quit water-pipe smoking and related factors. This means that the increased perception of between level of knowledge regarding the impact of water-pipe smoking on health leads to an increase in the intention to quit water-pipe smoking and related factors. (Al-Ruzzieh & Ayaad 2021; Jacob et al., 2013; Mamtani et al., 2017; Tucktuck et al., 2017; Waziry, et al., 2017).

Conclusion

The studies provide information regarding water pipe use among university students, which could be used as baseline information for more specific studies. The results showed the high cost of water pipe use per month

among students. The students used a water pipe with their friends for the first time especially the males and at the café for the first time. Most of the students had a water pipe at home and preferred a water pipe with flavour. Moreover, the results showed no significant difference between male and female studies in most studied variables. The main reasons and drivers were the increasing water-pipe use in times of stress such as exams as well as in relaxation such as holidays, smell enjoyment, getting rid of the stressors, and help in relaxation. The main attitudes and beliefs toward water-pipe smoking, according to students' perceptions, were feelings of being fond of water-pipe smoking. The students perceived that young people harm themselves by water-pipe smoking, and the community around them accepts water-pipe smoking more than cigarette smoking. The students perceived that water-pipe smoking could harm fetuses during pregnancy, may cause various types of cancer, may cause heart disease, and water-pipe smoke contains more tar than cigarette smoke. There was a significant positive relationship between attitudes and beliefs toward water-pipe use and the level of knowledge regarding the impact of water-pipe smoking on health, as well as a negative relationship between it and intention to quit water-pipe smoking and related factors. Moreover, there was a positive relationship between the level of knowledge regarding the impact of water-pipe smoking on health, and intention to quit water-pipe smoking and related factors.

Limitation and Recommendation

Many limitations challenged the researcher while conducting this research to attain the study goals. The limited time for data collection and the difficult acceptance of students restricted the data collection from more universities. For this reason, the generalisation of data to all Jordanian universities is restricted. Furthermore, many female students felt shame when filling out the questionnaire, which increased the number of students who were not interested in participating in the research. Finally, limited comprehensive studies and a lack of national databases regarding water among university students limited the understanding of study results.

Based on our study results, it was recommended that structured awareness programs regarding the risk of water-pipe use and stress management techniques for university students be developed. Moreover, it was recommended that a national or university-level database regarding water-pipe use be developed to monitor water-pipe use and related drivers among university students. Proper collaboration between the Ministry of Health, universities, the Ministry of Higher Education, and all stakeholders, as well as increasing the

university and Ministry of Higher Education's funding, was recommended to ensure the development of proper and comprehensive strategies to combat water-pipe use among university students. Finally, more studies at the national level discussing the water pipe, its impacts on academic achievements, students' psychological and physical health, and differential factors are recommended to increase the understanding of water pipe use and its relationships.

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